

INTRODUCTION TO SPECIAL EDITION OF FIDES ET LIBERTAS ON COVID-19 AND RELIGIOUS LIBERTY

THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC & RELIGIOUS FREEDOM

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1. THE PANDEMIC AND RELIGIOUS FREEDOM IN EUROPE AND AMERICA

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, governmental authorities across the globe have implemented unprecedented restrictions on public gatherings and collective social activities. These restrictions include the cancelation of major sporting events such as the 2020 Tokyo Olympics, the suspension of most international commercial travel, the postponement of political elections such as the second round of municipal polling in France, and the enforced closure of many businesses such as restaurants and concert halls. In many jurisdictions, these restrictions have also been applied to religious spaces and to communal religious practices. Whilst all state curtailments of rights and liberties merit critical scrutiny as to their legality and their legitimacy, restrictions imposed upon religious freedoms raise (at least) three specific concerns.

First, collective religious practices have been shown to play a uniquely powerful role in individuals' sense of self due to the compelling affective experiences and a moral authority associated with religious group membership (Luhtanen & Crocker, 1992; Wellman & Tokuno, 2004; Ysseldyk et al. 2010). Second, and relatedly, in cases where individuals consider access to religious spaces and participation in communal religious practices to constitute a moral obligation, such limitations can constitute a violation of their moral autonomy (REF). Finally, secular modernity is premised upon a fragile equilibrium between the power which the state exercises over the public sphere and the spaces of liberty accorded to religious expression and belief (REF); excessive restrictions by the state on religion risk disrupting that balance.

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Given the sensitive nature of religious practices and beliefs, numerous actors and organizations have contested the application of social distancing and restriction measures on religious spaces and practices. In the United States lawsuits have been filed against state and municipal governments in Kansas, Florida, Mississippi, Kentucky, Virginia, California and Texas.³ In Europe as well, the issue has led to confrontations between religious communities and governmental authorities, as in Greece⁴ and France⁵. However, because of the rapidly evolving nature of the COVID-19 crisis, and because of variances within legislative national frameworks, the full extent and nature of the current restrictions on in western countries is hard to assess.

In December of 2020, the International Religious Liberty Institute of Andrews University, located in southwest Michigan, teamed up with the University of Portsmouth and the Brigham Young University Center for Law and Religion Studies and sponsored a conference entitled “The COVID-19 Pandemic & Religious Freedom: Reports from North America and Europe.” It consisted of scholars from the United States, Canada, and several European countries, who gave papers on developments regarding COVID-19 restrictions and religious freedom in their respective geographical areas.

Fourteen papers were presented and commented on by a group consisting of somewhere between 30 and 40 scholars and lawyers from North America and Europe. The presentations and discussions were recorded, and can be found here: <https://www.covid-religiousliberty.org/events>. The presentation papers from the event are also made available at that site, but now for the first time these papers, revised in light of conference comments and editorial suggestions, are available in the present printed volume. Below we will spend a few moments commenting on the overall trajectory and message of the papers, one set from Europe, the other from America.

2. THE VIEW FROM EUROPE

During the first wave of the COVID-19 crisis in 2020, all EU states and the UK introduced some form of social distancing and/or confine-

3. <https://www.npr.org/sections/coronavirus-live-updates/2020/04/17/837698597/opposing-forced-church-closures-becomes-new-religious-freedom-cause>

4. <https://www.la-croix.com/Religion/Orthodoxie/Coronavirus-Grece-tensions-entre-lEglise-orthodoxe-gouvernement-2020-03-30-1201086859> ; <https://www.romfea.gr/diafora/36127-prosfugi-4-dikigoron-kata-ton-metron-pou-elifthisan-gia-tis-ekklisies>

5. <https://www.leparisien.fr/paris-75/a-paris-une-messe-pascale-clandestine-celebree-en-plein-confinement-12-04-2020-8298480.php>; <https://www.lefigaro.fr/vox/societe/l-appel-de-cent-trente-pretres-au-president-le-11-mai-laissez-nous-servir-20200424>

ment measures. However, European states did not respond to the situation in a uniform manner. Whilst they all referred to World Health Organization (WHO) recommendations⁶, and coordinated either multilaterally (for example through the European Council in the case of EU member states⁷) or bilaterally (for example, between the UK and France on border arrangements⁸), individual states established their public policy approaches autonomously.

Thus, Europe saw a wide spectrum of policy approaches in terms of the stringency of measures introduced to stem the propagation of the virus. On one end of the spectrum, Sweden adopted a relatively relaxed approach throughout the spring of 2020, maintaining many public liberties and favoring a “herd immunity” strategy⁹. In contrast, France¹⁰ and Spain¹¹, amongst other countries, quickly introduced a state of emergency, restricting a range of public liberties. At the opposite end of the spectrum, Estonia¹² and Romania¹³ went so far as to evoke Article 15 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), thereby derogating from certain obligations under the Convention.

Despite such latitude for national sovereignty in matters of health policy, COVID-19 containment policies adopted by EU states and the UK did converge on measures restricting religious liberty. The two most common measures in this regard were limitations imposed on collective religious practices and limitations imposed on access to places of worship; the details of which are examined in more detail, with reference to specific states, in the following articles. Whilst such measures (applied with varying levels of stringency) appear to have been the norm in Europe, Bulgaria and Hungary stood out as notable exceptions. In Bulgaria, although health authorities recommended the suspension of public religious celebrations, these recommendations were neither enforced by the government, nor voluntarily adopted by the Bulgarian Orthodox Church.¹⁴ Hungary is especially notable in this respect, having adopted measures to explicitly guarantee that restrictions on movement not hinder religious activities.¹⁵

6. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/technical-guidance>

7. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/43076/26-vc-euco-statement-en.pdf>

8. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/joint-statement-between-the-uk-and-france-10-may-2020>

9. [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(20\)31035-7/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(20)31035-7/fulltext)

10. <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/eli/loi/2020/5/11/PRMX2010645L/jo/texte>

11. <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2020/03/14/463/con>

12. <https://rm.coe.int/09000016809cfa87>

13. <https://rm.coe.int/09000016809cee30>

14. <https://orthodoxtimes.com/open-churches-in-bulgaria-the-services-are-also-broadcast-on-the-internet-and-radio/>

15. <http://abouthungary.hu/news-in-brief/coronavirus-update-restrictions-on-movement-now-in-force/>

Another major issue, discussed in the following articles, has been the impact of indirect curtailments on religious liberty: measures which have not specifically targeted religious groups or buildings, but which have, de facto, limited people's ability to gather in religious assemblies and engage in practices central to their religious beliefs. Thus, in Spain, Italy, and France, although religious organizations were, de jure, permitted to remain open and organize celebrations open to the public, in practice the police and local authorities limited these practices. Indeed, during the period of confinement in Spain, numerous incidents were reported of religious ceremonies being disrupted by the police throughout the country, despite their having respected the mandated minimal social distancing.¹⁶ In response to these interventions, the Spanish government faced complaints by numerous parties, including the Spanish Association for Christian Lawyers¹⁷ and the Spanish Observatory for Religious Freedom.¹⁸ Similar cases have been observed in Italy and France.

Since the first wave of the pandemic, several courts in European countries (in Germany, France, Belgium, England, and Scotland) have pushed back against the most stringent restrictions on religious liberty, for either procedural or substantive reasons. This is part of a larger trend that Mark Hill has described as a “steady stream of cases from around the world, now developing into something of a torrent, where the constitutionality of emergency provisions has been challenged”.¹⁹ Whilst the articles presented here offer a snapshot of the situation as it stood at the beginning of 2021, there is no doubt that the pandemic remains a present reality at the time of publication – and that its effects will be long-lasting in terms of how public authorities in Europe balance the protection of health with the preservation of fundamental liberties.

3. THE VIEW FROM NORTH AMERICA

The right to freedom of religion in the United States is protected primarily by the First Amendment to the federal constitution. The relevant text states that “Congress shall make no law respecting an establishment of

16. José Luis Bazán, “Religious Freedom in Spain during coronavirus pandemic: On the Abuses Committed by Spanish Public Authorities in the Implementation of Emergency Legislation Against COVID-19 that Undermine Religious Freedom”, Working Document, May 2020.

17. <https://abogadoscristianos.es/abogados-cristianos-se-querella-contra-el-ministro-marlaska-por-las-interrupciones-de-ceremonias-religiosas-realizadas-por-la-policia-durante-el-estado-de-alarma/>

18. <http://libertadreligiosa.es/2020/04/13/el-observatorio-para-la-libertad-religiosa-pide-explicaciones-al-ministro-del-interior-ante-la-suspension-de-misas-mientras-se-celebraban/>

19. Hill, M. Coronavirus and the Curtailment of Religious Liberty. *Laws*. 2020, 9, 27. <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws9040027>.

religion or prohibiting the free exercise thereof.” The first part is known as the establishment clause, and is generally understood as preventing governments, either federal or state, from supporting, promoting, or funding religion, or interfering in religious institutions. The second, known as the free exercise clause, is understood as protecting religious belief and behavior, of individuals and organizations alike.

Each state also has its own constitution, which typically contains its own version of these clauses. These state constitutions were largely ignored until the early 1990s, when the United States Supreme Court significantly cut-back on free exercise protections, protecting religious conduct only against laws that intentionally targeted religion. Since that time, state constitutions have received greater attention, as well as state laws passed to protect religious freedom, known as religious freedom restoration acts (RFRAs).²⁰ In responding to quarantine restrictions, then, people of faith need to consider a range of legal responses, from the federal and state constitutions, to state RFRA laws.

A number of papers discuss the constitutional challenges that have taken place against COVID restrictions, with some presenters arguing that the restrictions are legally justified, and others arguing that in a number of places there has been governmental overreach. Much of the discussion revolved around the question of how “essential” in-person religious gatherings are to both religious practice, as well as to the functions of civil society.

Discussion was also had about questions of equality of treatment between secular and religious activities. There did appear to be a general agreement that such equality of treatment was constitutionally called for, but disagreement about what secular activities were truly comparable to religious worship. Are gatherings in churches similar or different from gathering in casinos and bars, or shopping centers and stores, or airports and bus stations?

Several papers looked at the question of how best to balance public health and religious freedom. Should the equal treatment of religion with similar secular activities be the sole test? Or should there be a category of religious worship behavior that received “strict scrutiny” protection irrespective of whether secular counterparts existed? Also, the importance of trying to weigh and balance these matters ahead of legal challenges was emphasized. In other words, it is important that the legislative process re-

20. Miller, Nicholas, Sheers, Nathan, “Religious Free Exercise Under State Constitutions,” 34 *Journal of Church and State* 303 (1992).

ceive input from religious groups before the restrictions are implemented.

Some interesting observations were made regarding the pandemic, political affiliations and religion. The Democratic Party has been known, for the last couple of decades especially, to have somewhat lower sensitivity to members or views of traditional faith communities. This is in part due to strong stands taken by Democratic candidates and platforms in the areas of life and abortion, gender and sexuality, or religious freedom in comparison to LGBT+ concerns.²¹ Conversely, since the days of Ronald Reagan, Republicans have made inroads into the mainstream, evangelical Christian community. This trend has only been exacerbated in the last decade or two.²²

These two political affiliations are often connected with either pro-vaccine positions (Democrats) or vaccine hesitancy and opposition. (Republicans). This is not of course universally true, President Trump and his wife were vaccinated secretly before they left office, and it is reported that all fifty governors, both Democrat and Republican are vaccinated. But the ex-President was soundly booed at a Republican rally recently when he promoted the vaccine, and outbreaks of the COVID Delta variant are most intense, and vaccine rates most generally low, in red counties and states.

4. CONCLUDING THOUGHTS

At the time of writing, with the onslaught of the Delta variant, the progression of the virus continues to evolve at speed across Europe and the US, and state responses to the pandemic remain dynamic. What was thought to be an emerging from the woods at the beginning of the summer of 2021 for many western countries, has turned back into the masking, distancing, and quarantining slog of a year ago. Therefore, the discussion provided here serves as a point of departure which must be updated as the crisis develops in order to capture increases and decreases in restrictiveness.

It may be that states with currently have very high levels of restric-

21. David E. Campbell, Geoffrey C. Layman, *The Politics of Secularism in the United States: Class, Status and Power*. Political Power, 08 November 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118900772.etrds0423>

22. Legee DC, Kellstedt LA, editors (1993) *Rediscovering the religious factor in American politics*. New York: M.E. Sharpe, Inc.; Green JC (2007) *The faith factor: How religion influences American elections*. Westport, Connecticut: Praeger; Green JC, Kellstedt LA, Smidt CE, Guth JL (2007) How the faithful voted: Religious communities and the presidential vote. In Campbell DE, editor. *A matter of faith: Religion in the 2004 presidential election*. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Institution Press. 15–36; Bradberry LA (2016) *The Effect of Religion on Candidate Preference in the 2008 and 2012 Republican Presidential Primaries*. *PLoS ONE* 11(4): e0152037. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0152037>.

tiveness will soon reinstate religious liberties as the public health threat dissipates. It may also be that other states will increase and/or maintain current levels of restrictiveness indefinitely, thereby normalizing the state of exception; this latter scenario appears to be playing out in Hungary, where the parliament has passed a law allowing the Prime Minister to rule by decree without a set time limit.

In addition to such monitoring which needs to take place over the coming months, we also need to look deeper into the national contexts in which such restrictions are implemented. Part of this work requires an in-depth analysis of the “eco-system” of emergency COVID-19 legislation. Whilst states may impose relatively few direct restrictions on religious liberties, they may have other restrictions which impact on collective religious practice.

For example, whilst France has not explicitly ordered the closure of places of worship, the severe restrictions it places on residents’ movements may prohibit observant religious persons in France from exercising their right to visit places of worship. There may also exist arbitrary variances in implantation within countries where some regions or minority groups are subject to greater restrictions than others. Finally, religious freedoms are not unique in being severely restricted in these extraordinary times. As western states continue to suspend basic liberties in the name of public health, scholarly vigilance and civic engagement will be crucial for safeguarding the rule of law.

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